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RESULTS OF TREATMENT WITH ACUTE GASTRIC BLEEDING DUE TO STOMACH TUMORS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents data including an assessment of the choice of surgical treatment tactics and their effectiveness in patients with acute gastric bleeding due to stomach tumors. Indications for emergency surgery were: ongoing bleeding, ineffectiveness of endoscopic hemostasis. In addition to these indications, the risk of recurrent bleeding was taken into account; if the risk was high, urgent surgery was performed after complete preoperative preparation. At the height of profuse gastric bleeding, emergency surgical interventions were performed in 15 out of 31 patients. In case of bleeding gastric cancer, surgical tactics should be aimed at eliminating its source, both radically and palliatively, even if the tumor has invaded neighboring organs, and should be carried out in compliance with all modern oncological principles.

Key words: gastric bleeding, stomach cancer, treatment methods.

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OSHQOZON O'SMALARIDAN O'TKIR QON KETISHINING DAVOLASH NATIJALARI**ANNOTATSIYA**

Maqolada oshqozon o'smalari tufayli oshqozondan o'tkir qon ketishi bilan og'rigan bemorlarda jarrohlik davolash taktikasini tanlash va ularning samaradorligini baholash kabi ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Shoshilinch operatsiyalar uchun ko'rsatmalarga: davom etayotgan qon ketish, endoskopik gemostazning samarasizligi xizmat qildi. Ushbu ko'rsatmalarga qo'shimcha ravishda, takroriy qon ketish xavfi hisobga olindi, agar xavf yuqori bo'lsa, operatsiyadan oldingi to'liq tayyorgarlikdan so'ng shoshilinch operatsiya o'tkazildi. Oshqozondan aktiv qon ketishida 31 bemordan 15 tasida shoshilinch jarrohlik aralashuvlar amalga oshirildi. Me'da saratoni tufayli qon ketishida jarrohlik taktikasi, hatto o'simta qo'shni a'zolariga o'sib kirib ketgan bo'lsa ham, uning manbasini ham radikal va palliativ yo'l bilan yo'q qilishga qaratilgan bo'lishi va barcha zamonaviy onkologiya tamoyillariga muvofiq amalga oshirilishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: oshqozondan qon ketishi, oshqozon saratoni, davolash usullari.

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РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ С ОСТРЫМ ЖЕЛУДОЧНЫМ КРОВОТЕЧЕНИЕМ ОБУСЛОВЛЕННЫЕ С ОПУХОЛЯМИ ЖЕЛУДКА**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье представлены данные включающие оценку выбора хирургической лечебной тактики и их эффективности у больных с острыми желудочными кровотечениями при опухолях желудка. Показаниями к экстренной операции были: продолжающееся кровотечение, неэффективность эндоскопического гемостаза. Помимо данных показаний учитывали риск рецидива кровотечения, при высоком риске выполняли срочную операцию после полноценной предоперационной подготовки. На высоте профузного желудочного кровотечения экстренные оперативные вмешательства произвели 15 больным из 31. При кровоточащем раке желудка оперативная тактика должно быть направлено на устранение его источника как радикально так и паллиативно даже при прорастании опухоли в соседние органы и должна быть выполнена с соблюдением всех современных онкологических принципов.

Ключевые слова: желудочное кровотечение, рак желудка, методы лечения.

Mavzuning dolzarbligi. Turli manbalarining ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, bir necha yillik kuzatuvlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, oshqozon saratonidan qon ketishi, barcha oshqozondan qon ketishlarning 5,1 dan 22,4% gachasini tashkil etadi [1,4,8,10]. Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, oshqozon saratoni bilan kasallanish dunyodagi saraton kasalliklari orasida tashxis qo'yilgan holatlar soni bo'yicha beshinchi va o'lim darajasi bo'yicha ikkinchi o'rinda turadi. Ushbu onkopatologiyani murakkablashtiradigan oshqozon-ichakdan qon ketishida o'lim darajasi 30% ga etadi [4, 5]. Ko'pgina mualliflar oshqozon o'smalarining yemirilishida qon ketishini to'xtatishning qiyinchiliklari haqida aytib o'tishgan [2,5,7,12]. Ularning ta'kidlashicha, tomirlarga klips qo'yilganda to'qimalarning kuchli infiltratsiyasi tufayli klisalar bo'shashib ketishi va koagulyatsiya ishlatilganda esa ko'pincha qon ketishining

kuchayishi kuzatilgan. Yaxshi gemostatik taʼsir qon ketish joyiga mahalliy ravishda etanolni inʼeksiya qilib chiqish, keyinchalik, bir muncha vaqt oʻtgach, ditsinon qilinganida qayd etilgan[3,9,11]. Oshqozon saratonini jarrohlik yoʻli bilan davolashda asosiy jarrohlik operatsiyasi gastrektomiya hisoblanadi. Qoʻllanilishi va asoratlari nuqtai nazaridan, bu operatsiya eng qiyin hisoblanadi va anastomoz choklarining etishmovchiligi operatsiyadan keyingi oʻlimning asosiy sabablaridan biri boʻlib qolmoqda [10,11,12]. Shuni taʼkidlash kerakki, shoshilinch jarrohlikda gastrektomiya shoshilinch va shu bilan birga majburiy jarrohlik aralashuvi boʻlib, koʻpchilik jarrohlar ushbu toifadagi bemorlarda operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlarni rivojlanish xavfi yuqori boʻlganligi sababli oʻta ehtiyotkorlik bilan yondashishadi. Bemorlarning 60-80% kasallikning oxirgi bosqichlarida va ogʻir asoratlari kuzatilganda davolanish uchun murojaat qilishadi. Baʼzi hollarda, oshqozon oʻsmalarining teshilishi natijasida rivojlangan peritonit bilan ogʻrigan bemorlarda, shuningdek, onologik kasalliklarga chalingan bemorlarning 15% dan koʻprogʻida uchraydigan oshqozondan profuz qon ketish vaqtida majburiy gastrektomiya qilish kerak boʻladi [6,12,13].

Gastrektomiya natijalari koʻp jihatdan bemorni tayyorlashga va qiziloʻngach-ichak anastomozini shakllantirish usulini tanlashga bogʻliq. Bugungi kunga qadar ushbu anastomozni shakllantirishning koʻplab usullari taklif qilingan, ammo ularning hech biri xavfli asoratlardan, ayniqsa qiziloʻngach-ichak anastomozining choklari yetishmovchiligini yuzaga kelmasligini kafolatlamaydi. Qiziloʻngach-ichak anastomozini shakllantirishning optimal variantini tanlash masalasi munozarali boʻlib qolmoqda. Muhokama mavzusi qiziloʻngach-ichak anastomozini germetikligini yanada ishonchli usullarini izlash boʻlib qoladi, bu nafaqat qoniqarli bajarilishi, balki uzoq muddatli natijalarni ham berishi lozim boʻladi.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi - oshqozon oʻsmalari tufayli oshqozondan oʻtkir qon ketishi bilan ogʻrigan bemorlarda davolash taktikasini tanlash va ularning samaradorligini baholash.

Materiallar va usullar. Tadqiqot materiali oshqozon saratoni bilan ogʻrigan bemorlarni jarrohlik yoʻli bilan davolash, katta charvini olib tashlash va baʼzi hollarda koʻndalang chamber ichak tutqichini rezeksiya qilish hamda limfa tugunlarini D2 disseksiyasi bilan kombinatsiyalashgan gastrektomiyani natijalarini tahlil qilishga asoslangan. Oʻtgan 10 yilda Respublika shoshilinch tibbiy yordam ilmiy markazi Samarqand filiali jarrohlik boʻlimlari va filiallarida 31 nafar bemorga qon ketishi bilan asoratlangan oshqozon oʻsmasi boʻyicha shoshilinch gastrektomiya operatsiyasi oʻtkazildi. Bemorlarning yoshi 39 yoshdan 71 yoshgacha boʻlgan. Ularning 15 nafari (48,4 foizi) erkaklar va 16 nafari (51,6 foizi) ayollardir.

Biz oshqozon yarasini aniqlash uchun Jonson tasnifidan foydalandik. Meʼdadan oʻtkir qon ketishining sababi 6 holatda subkardiyaning yirik kallyoz yarasi, 7 holatda - oshqozon tanasining katta egriligi old devori boʻylab saratonning yarali-infiltrativ shakli, 6 holatda - oshqozon tanasining katta egriligi orqa devori boʻylab yarali-infiltrativ shakli, 12 holatda – oshqozonni piloroantral sohasidanligi aniqlandi. 6 ta holatda oshqozon saratonining yarali-infiltrativ shakli koʻndalang chamber ichak tutqichiga oʻsgan (1-jadval).

1-jadval.

Oshqozon hajmli hosilalarining lokalizatsiyasi

Oshqozon saratoni lokalizatsiyasi	Bemorlar soni	
	Abs	%
Katta egrilikning oldingi devorida	7	22,7
Oshqozon tanasining orqa devorida	6	19,3
Oshqozoning subkardial qismida	6	19,3
Piloroantral sohada	12	38,7
Jami	31	100

Barcha bemorlar shifoxonaga yotqizilgandan soʻng dastlabki soatlarda gastroduodenofibroskopiya tekshirishidan oʻtkazildi. Qon ketishini baholashda Forest boʻyicha endoskopik tasnif qoʻllanildi, 15 (48,4%) bemorda arterial qon ketish (FIa) va 1 bemorda ikkita yirik "qarama-qarshi" malignizatsiyalashgan oshqozon yarasidan venoz qon ketish (FIb), 9 (29,1%) bemorlarda (FIIa), 6 nafar (19,4%) bemorlarda (FIIb) aniqlandi.

Natijalar va uning muhokamasi. Bemorlarning barchasi ko‘p qon yo‘qotilishi tufayli og‘ir ahvolda olib kelingan.

Koagulyatsiya orqali qon ketishini to‘xtatish uchun endoskopik urinishlar 30 (96,8%) holatda amalga oshirildi, amaliyot samaradorligi 50% ni tashkil etdi. Koagulyatsiya bilan birga qon ketish joyiga 96% etil spirti bilan endoskopik in‘eksiya qilish qo‘llanilgan. Bundan tashqari, barcha bemorlarga gemostatik terapiya tavsiya etilgan. Qon komponentlarini qo‘llash bilan kompleks konservativ davolash 16 (51,6%) bemorda vaqtincha samarali bo‘ldi. 15 (48,4%) holatda konservativ va endoskopik usullar bilan davolash samarasiz bo‘lgan. Bizning fikrimizcha, oshqozondan profuz qon ketishida konservativ davolash va endoskopik gemostazga erishish imkonsizligi, qon ketishi manbasining chap me‘da va pankreatoduodenal arteriyalarning yirik tarmoqlari bo‘lganligi bilan bog‘liq edi.

Shoshilinch jarrohlik uchun ko‘rsatmalarga davom etayotgan qon ketish, endoskopik gemostazning samarasizligi xizmat qildi. Ushbu ko‘rsatmalarga qo‘shimcha ravishda, agar takroriy qon ketishi xavf yuqori bo‘lsa, xavf hisobga olinib, to‘liq operatsiyadan oldingi tayyorgarlikdan so‘ng shoshilinch operatsiya o‘tkazildi.

Oshqozondan profuz qon ketishining yuqori cho‘qqisida 31 bemordan 15 tasida shoshilinch jarrohlik aralashuvlar amalga oshirildi. Bundan tashqari, ularning barchasi oshqozondan profuz qon ketishi boshlanganidan boshlab dastlabki 1-3 soat ichida operatsiya qilingan, endoskopik gemostazning muvaffaqiyatsiz urinishidan keyin qolgan bemorlarga vaqtincha konservativ va endoskopik gemostazdan keyingi 2-3 kun ichida jarrohlik muolajalari o‘tkazildi. Ushbu bemorlardagi operatsiyalar operatsiyadan oldingi ma‘lum tayyorgarlikdan so‘ng yanada qulay sharoitda o‘tkazildi.

Deyarli barcha holatlarda katta charvini olib tashlash va ba‘zi hollarda ko‘ndalang chamber ichak tutqichini rezeksiya qilish hamda limfa tugunlarini D2 disseksiyasi bilan kombinatsiyalashgan gastrektomiya amalga oshirildi. Bemorlarda taloqni saqlab qolgan holda D2 hajmda limfa tugunlarini disseksiya qilish amalga oshirildi. Gastrektomiya paytida D2 limfa tugunlarini disseksiya qilish uchun taloqni saqlovchi texnikaning mohiyati parapankreatik to‘qimalarni va taloq arteriyasi va venasi bo‘ylab (11-guruh limfa tugunlari) taloq darvozasigacha (10-guruh limfa tugunlari) ketma-ket olib tashlandi.

Oshqozon o‘smasining taloqqa, oshqozon-taloq boylamining infiltratsiyasi yoki taloq tomirlari bo‘ylab va taloq darvozasida joylashgan metastatik limfa tugunlariga o‘sishi gastrektomiya paytida splenektomiya qilishga majbur bo‘lindi. Bunday vaziyatda splenektomiya kombinatsiyalashgan jarrohlik aralashuvining ajralmas qismi sifatida mutlaq ko‘rsatmalarga muvofiq amalga oshirildi. Kombinatsiyalashgan gastrektomiyadan so‘ng barcha bemorlarga M.I.Davidov modifikatsiyasiga ko‘ra, ezofagoeyunoanastomoz quyish va ingichka ichakdan rezervuar hosil qilindi (1-rasm).

1-chi modifikatsiya
1-rasm. M.I.Davidov modifikatsiyasi

2-chi modifikatsiya

Operativ aralashuv vaqtida yomon sifatli o'smaning morfologik tuzilishini aniqlash imkoniyati faqat kechiktirilgan operatsiyalarda mavjud edi. Adenokarsinoma 27 (87,1%) klinik holatda aniqlangan. Boshqa hollarda, yassi hujayrali, kichik hujayrali va differensatsiyalashmagan saraton turlari aniqlangan.

Jarrohlik yo'li bilan davolash natijalarini baholashda biz operatsiya vaqtida va operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlarni, uzoq muddatli natijalarni, shuningdek, operatsiya qilingan bemorlarning hayot sifatini baholadik. Operatsiya vaqtidagi asoratlarni tahlil qilganda, 28 (90,3%) bemorda operatsiyalar texnik qiyinchiliklarsiz amalga oshirilganligi va intraoperativ asoratlar kuzatilmaganligini aniqladik. 3 (9,7%) bemorda qon ketish yoki taloqning shikastlanishi kabi turli xil intraoperatsion asoratlar kuzatildi. Bizning kuzatuvlarimizda, taloqning shikastlanishi oshqozon mobilizatsiyasi paytida va limfa tugunlarining disseksiyasi vaqtidagi tortilish natijasida yuzaga keldi. Bunday turdagi asorat 2 (6,5%) holatda kuzatilib, qon ketishi splenektomiya bajarilishi bilan to'xtatildi.

Operatsiya qilingan 31 nafar bemorlarning bittasida (3,2%) o'lim bilan yakunlanganini qayd etildi. Operatsiyadan keyingi erta davrda bemorda qizilo'ngach-oshqozon anastomozdagi choklar yetishmovchiligi ko'rinishidagi asorat kuzatilib, bu esa o'limga olib keldi.

Operatsiyadan keyingi davrda barcha bemorlar standart davolashdan o'tkazildi: suv-elektrolitlar va kislotasi-ishqor muvozanatini nazorat qilish, donor qon komponentlarini tomir ichiga yuborish, keng qamrovli antibakterial terapiya, shuningdek, yo'ldosh kasalliklarni korreksiya qilish bajarildi. Nazoeyunal zondni olib tashlash operatsiyadan keyingi o'rtacha 8-9 kunlar ichida amalga oshirildi. 9-10 kundan keyin og'iz orqali ovqatlanishga (suyuqlik qabul qilish, ozuqaviy aralashmalar va boshqalar) ruxsat etildi.

Ushbu bemorlarni davolash natijalarini tahlil qilish quyidagilarni ko'rsatdi:

- Operatsiyadan keyingi davrda agastral sindromning yo'qligi.
- Malabsorbsiya sindromining yo'qligi.
- Bemorlarda sog'lom odamlar kabi to'yish va ochlik hissi paydo bo'ladi.
- Diariya sindromining yo'qligi.
- Tana massasi defitsitining kam ifodalanishi.
- Refluks ezofagit kam kuzatilishi.

Oshqozon saratoni rivojlanish xususiyatlariga qarab bemorlarning 5 yillik yashab qolish va hayot sifatini batafsil tahlil qilish shuni ko'rsatdiki, T1-T2 bosqichlarida ekzofitik o'sish shakli, yuqori differensatsiyalashgan adenokarsinomada bemorlarning uzoq muddatli yashab qolish darajasi ancha yaxshiroq bo'ldi. O'simta invaziyasi chuqurligining oshishi, ayniqsa oshqozon devorining seroz qoplamiga kirishi bilan, o'smaning infiltrativ shakli, kam differensatsiyalashgan adenokarsinoma va uzuksimon hujayrali saratoni bilan bemorlarda yashab qolish darajasi va hayot sifati yomonlashishi kuzatildi.

Xulosa: Oshqozon saratoni qon ketishida jarrohlik taktikasi, hatto o'simta qo'shni a'zolari qamrab olgan bo'lsa ham, uning manbasini ham tubdan, ham palliativ yo'l bilan yo'q qilishga qaratilgan bo'lishi kerak va barcha zamonaviy onkologik tamoyillarga rioya qilgan holda amalga oshirilishi kerak.

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